

METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM FOR IMPROVING THE VALEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article highlights the importance of valeological skills of the biology teacher, the functions of application and the modern pedagogical capabilities of the teaching methodology of biology. In the innovative activities of teaching, it is aimed at increasing biological knowledge, exchange of ideas. The development of sanogenic thinking on ensuring the health and well-being of young people in the preparation of future biology teachers for professional and pedagogical activities, in the content of biological education, valeological skills are recognized as the main factor that ensures sustainable development.*

Keywords: *didactic fundamentals of teaching biology educational subjects, forms of teaching, professional pedagogical activity, valeological competence, pedagogical capabilities.*

Introduction. In our republic, wide opportunities are being created to reform the preparation of future educators for professional pedagogical activity on the basis of innovative approaches, to strengthen the educational and methodological support for the formation and development of valeological thinking (healthy lifestyle) skills. The concept of development of the public education system until 2030 established such priorities as “creation of new generations of didactic materials and multimedia products intended for in-depth study of Biological Sciences, spiritual and moral education of students, ensuring their physically healthy and energetic formation, popularizing the principles of healthy nutrition for students of Secondary Schools”². Based on these tasks, it is important to identify the content of the conceptual foundations of the content of valeological skills, develop vitagenic and sanogenic thinking by teaching students to protect against addictive behavior and correctly analyze their vital activity, and create an innovative educational technology-based methodological system. Based on these tasks, the future biology will be able to determine the didactic content of innovation technologies for improving valeological competence in teachers, to determine the didactic content of developing valeological competence in the content of the methodology of teaching biology, to determine the didactic content of developing valeological competence in the content of teaching biology, to, provides the ability to manage a methodological system based on the content of skills and competencies in continuity and consistency.

Analysis of thematic literature (Literature review). The study of the content and essence of existing sources justifies the fact that as early as the first period of our society, social practical actions were taken in relation to improving the human lifestyle, creating criteria for determining a healthy lifestyle among the population [2]. Issues such as the formation of the spiritual culture of the student youth, the education of a perfect person on the basis of the idea of national independence, the preparation of young people for an independent family on the basis of valeological (healthy lifestyle), the formation of healthy beliefs and national immunity

M.Inamova, N.D.Ishniyozova, O.Musurmonova, I.M.Mirziyotov, M.Quranov, B.Ziyamuhmedov, G.U.Salikhova, O.Fayziev, D.SHaripova, M.M.Researched by isabaeva et al.

In the formation of healthy lifestyle skills in students, the content of environmental knowledge has gained an important place, and a number of research works dedicated to these problems have arisen. X of the methodology for the formation of ecological taffakkur in schoolchildren.A.Rakhmatova, A.S.To ' khtaev, A.Hamidov, H.B.Norbotaev and T.T.Saparov noted that the implementation of teaching technologies aimed at maintaining the health of schoolchildren in ecologically unfavorable regions, X.O.In the scientific research work of shaykhova, the study of the ethical aspects of creating a healthy lifestyle, the effective form, methods and means of educating elementary students in an ecological spirit in the extracurricular educational process M.B.Research by rakhimkulova [7], I.Khakimov noted that scientific pedagogical analysis of the peculiarities of a healthy environment in the maturation of a healthy generation, SH.B.Irgashev, L.A.Tursunkhojaeva, SH.In the organization of a healthy lifestyle, it is important in our research work that physical activity, work and rest are at a moderate level, normative nutrition, as well as scientific coverage of the direct impact of environmental conditions on health.

Research Methodology (Research Methodology). The problem of developing valeological competence (healthy lifestyle) of the future biology teacher was studied on the basis of innovative approaches in the content of scientific pedagogical, psychological, medical and biological education, which serves as a methodological resource in this research activity. Valeological competence (healthy lifestyle) requires a biology teacher to have the ability to plan a system of pedagogical competence, innovative activity and training for educational work in the content of healthy lifestyle skills in the content of biological education.

In the preparation of future biology teachers for professional pedagogical activity in pedagogical higher educational institutions, the organization of “biology teaching methodology”, science and effective practices on the basis of 4+2 is widely established, which plays an important role. [1] Professional educational knowledge in students in the teaching of these subjects introduces the development of activities, the content and structure of biological education, the possibilities of updating the content of education related to valeological competence (healthy lifestyle) on the basis of modern approaches. This biology knowledge of the teaching, processes, pedagogical principles and laws related to the basics of science, allows the teacher to organize and control educational processes related to concepts related to valeology in the content of the school biology course in accordance with the requirements of the Times. This opportunity in the Educational Sciences of biology it is advisable to define the didactic foundations for the content of valeological (healthy lifestyle) competence as follows.

1. The use of methodological foundations for the formation of valeological (healthy lifestyle) competence in all forms of teaching biology on the basis of an integrative approach to education.

2. Restoration of biological knowledge-the restoration of valeological knowledge through educational, educational and developmental goals in the content of biological education, teaching analytical and logical thinking.

3. Updating biological knowledge-to expand the previously acquired knowledge of a healthy lifestyle, to develop it on the basis of clear evidence.

4 correction of biological knowledge-analysis of the knowledge acquired on valeology and elimination of allowed shortcomings.

The main concepts of valeology include valeological education, valeological teaching, valeological (upbringing, valeological knowledge, valeological culture. Valeological information refers to the continuity of education, education and development of a healthy generation in terms of scientific and practical knowledge and the formation of skills, behavioral and activity systems, ensuring a valuable attitude to their own health and the health of those around them [6]. The professional skills of the biology teacher, such as analyzing the factors of a healthy lifestyle in the content of Science, the formation of a motivational environment in training sessions, are armed with knowledge that is responsible for maintaining biological health in students.

Analysis and Results (Analysis and results). The analysis of scientific research and scientific and methodological literature in our country and abroad shows that a number of works have been carried out on the formation of a healthy lifestyle in students. L.N.Bashmakova, B.M.SHapiro, G.U.In kurmanova's research work, it is important that a healthy lifestyle illuminates ways to protect against various diseases in the active survival of the organism as a factor in ensuring the health of a person mentally, physically [4]. D.J.In Sharipova's research, the problems of organizing a healthy lifestyle on the basis of the fundamentals of valeology of students, hygienic education are highlighted, with special attention to the disclosure of the essence of research on the organization of hygienic education, as well as the development of experimental content on the organization of hygienic education in a holistic system [6]. After all, the approach in this way provides the basis for the formation of a clear tassavur on the nature of the research work.

In our research work, biology consists in clarifying the competence content of the development of valeological competence in the preparation of teachers for professional activities, developing educational cognitive activity on the basis of innovative technologies, as well as developing a system of didactic tasks that determine students' creative activity in determining the degree of content of healthy lifestyle skills [3]. It is observed that the effective use of these didactic tasks gives an effective result in educational technologies that promote vitagenic, reflexive, health and sanogenic thinking. In the development of the study, the following pedagogical possibilities for determining the didactic purpose of innovative technologies and being able to select valeological knowledge for content and implement it into the process were identified in the development of a structural project of the lesson: the effective use of methods, tools and technologies for finding a healthy lifestyle skill in all forms of; biology makes the priority of the problem of finding a healthy lifestyle skill in students by effectively organizing and developing this process the basis for the satisfaction of the need of our society for a highly spiritual, educated and potential, harmonious person[5].

Conclusions and suggestions (Conclusion/Recommendations). Didactic fundamentals of improving valeological competence in the future biology teacher are manifested in educational continuity and form the basis of the work to be studied in future biology improving valeological competence in future biology teachers on the basis of educational technologies that develop vitagenic, reflexive, health and sanogenic thinking, didactic functions of valeological competence in future biology teachers - improved on the basis of educational technologies that promote knowledge renewal, knowledge correction, knowledge adherence, prediction, vitagenic, reflexive, health preservation and sanogenic thinking.

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